

System Requirements

1. Functional Requirement

ID	RF001
Name	Enter Source Code
Priority	High
Description	The system should allow the user to enter the source code in the programming field.

ID	RF002
Name	View Diagram in Real Time
Priority	High
Description	The system should show the diagram generated by the source code in real time.

ID	RF003
Name	Code in Python
Priority	High
Description	The system must only allow the user to program the source code in the Python language.

ID	RF005
Name	Save Diagram
Priority	High
Description	The system should allow the user to download the diagram in the PNG extension.

ID	RF007
Name	User Manual
Priority	Medium
Description	The system must have a tab with its operating instructions in a descriptive way.

ID	RF008
Name	Recognize Keywords
Priority	Medium
Description	The system must be able to interpret the commands inserted in the source code by the user.

ID	RF009
Name	Save Source Code in Python
Priority	High
Description	The system should allow the user to download the Python code referring to the diagram.

ID	RF010
Name	Show Examples
Priority	High
Description	The system should allow the user to view different examples of diagrams in Python code.

ID	RF011
Name	Error Log
Priority	High
Description	The system must allow the user to see the compilation errors.

2. Non-Functional Requirement

ID	RNF001
Name	Screen Reading
Priority	High
Description	The system must allow the NVDA software to read the screen and its components.

ID	RNF002
Name	Internet Access
Priority	High
Description	The system should be accessed by anyone with an internet connection.

ID	RNF003
Name	Real Time Update
Priority	Medium
Description	The system must update and compile information in real time.

ID	RNF004
Name	Intuitive System
Priority	High
Description	The system must have a simple, lean and intuitive interface, to facilitate screen reading by NVDA.